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Justification of Calculation of Illegal Drug Consumption

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Abstract

The drug situation monitoring system in Russia uses data on the number of drugs withdrawn from circulation in a weight indicator. However, this does not reflect the real extent of the danger, since differences in the activity of substances and population density of different administrative districts are not taken into account. Based on the analysis of statistical data, a methodology for calculating the prevalence of drugs based on the determination of conventional doses that are multiples of the size of the narcotic drugs, determining the onset of criminal liability and determining their prevalence in the territory of the administrative district per 100,000 population is proposed.

Keywords: Narcotic drugs; Methodology for calculating seized psychoactive substances; Drug situation; Drug monitoring

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Determining the extent of the illicit distribution and consumption of narcotic drugs is one of the goals of monitoring the drug situation [5]. Among the sources of information about the extent of their proliferation appear and information about illegal traffic seizure of psychoactive substances (PAS) at the moment of criminal case [3]. The annual reports of the Russian State Anti-Narcotics

Committee provide data on the weight of seized surfactants, while the degree of danger of individual drugs is not reflected [2]. As a result of this approach, an opinion is formed that the most common are the drugs of the cannabis group, which do not represent a significant social danger. In addition, differences in population in administrative districts are not taken into

account. Thus, the modernization of methodological approaches to assessing the illegal distribution and consumption of surfactants is required, as, for example, this has already been proposed when taking into account the extent of alcohol-attributive mortality [6].

The purpose of the study is to justify the use of the methodology for calculating the amount of surfactants seized to determine the extent of their illegal distribution and consumption.

Materials and Research Methods:

Analyzed special forms of interagency statistical reporting for 2015-2018 in the Russian Federation (RF). The data were converted into conventional doses in accordance with the established sizes of surfactants that determine the onset of criminal liability. Prevalence rates were calculated per 100,000 administrative district populations. Statistical processing of the research results was carried out using the SPSS 22.0 program. The search for linear relationships between the two features was carried out using the Pearson correlation coefficient.

The results of the study: For the period 2015-2018, Russian law enforcement authorities withdrawn from circulation more than 100 000 kg of PAS (Table. 1).

Table 1: The number of PAS seized by major groups for 2015-2018 in weight indicator (in kg).					
Years	Opiates	Cannabinoids	Amphetamines	Cocaine	“Spice”
2015	3 170.3	23 438.5	3 383.7	954.5	1 490.2
2016	1 411.0	15 084.1	2 400.4	143.7	710.4
2017	977.3	14 346.8	4 490.9	442.9	518.1
2018	1 161.5	15 202.9	3 457.1	47.6	365.7

For the recalculation, we used the parameters of the PAS size, which are minimal for the formation of the offense and the onset of criminal liability (Table 2) [4].

Table 2: Minimal dimensions of narcotic drugs and plants for the formation of the offense and the onset of criminal liability (kg)			
PAS	The size (in kg)	PAS	The size (in kg)
Opium group			
Poppy straw	0.02	Opium	0.001
Acetylated Opium	0,0005	Morphine	0.0001
Heroin	0,0005	Desomorphine	0.00005
Sleeping pills	0.02		
Cannabis group			
Cannabis	0.006	Hashish	0.002
Cannabis oil	0,0004	Hemp	0.006
Amphetamine group			
MDMA	0,0006	Methamphetamine	0,0003
Ephedron	0,0002	Mephedrone	0,0002
N-Methylephedrone	0,0002		
Other narcotic drugs			
Cocaine	0,0005	Synthetic cannabinoids	0.00005

The calculation was carried out according to the formula:

Conditional dose (c.d.) = weight / size (Table 3).

Table 3: The number of PAS seized by major groups for 2015-2018 (c.d.)					
Years	Opiates	Cannabinoids	Amphetamines	Cocaine	“Spice”
2015	4 091 084	5 780 906	15 976 117	1 909 082	29 804 160
2016	1 978 608	3 801 500	10 843 087	287 490	14 208 660
2017	1 077 322	3 574 850	19 267 123	885 844	10 362 460
2018	1 478 612	3 913 087	15 595 920	95 106	7 313 120

To assess the prevalence of PAS in administrative districts, seizure rates in arbitrary doses were recalculated to the level and prevalence according to the formula [1] (Table 4):

Prevalence = c.d. * 100,000 / population of the administrative district

Table 4: Levels of prevalence for major PAS groups for 2015-2018 by administrative district (in urban units per 100,000 population).					
Years	Opiates	Cannabinoids	Amphetamines	Cocaine	Spice
Russian Federation					
2015	2 797	3 952	10 923	1 305	20 377
2016	1 350	2 594	7 399	196	9 696
2017	734	2 435	13 124	603	7 059
2018	1 007	2 666	10 624	65	4 982
Central District					
2015	6 821	2 088	5 742	160	23 531
2016	2 086	1 175	5 697	79	18 223
2017	1 357	1 010	15 519	1 926	4 389
2018	2 301	1 131	14 310	38	1 178
Northwest District					
2015	372	3 157	3 897	11 014	12 409
2016	372	2 262	1 656	23	6 430
2017	717	950	31 196	112	3 994
2018	93	2 500	2 100	185	5 812
North Caucasus District					
2015	422	2 720	1 179	0	4 187
2016	505	1 862	2 183	1	906
2017	351	1 075	1 170	2	572
2018	359	1 096	1 768	1	307
Southern District					
2015	732	3 330	4 346	38	4 852
2016	188	1 529	4 490	3	1 250
2017	368	1 654	4 409	453	2 503
2018	256	1 046	4 474	7	1 259
Volga region					
2015	871	1 361	19 820	7	18 863
2016	1 550	605	5 689	3	5 818

2017	435	651	5 369	11	9 107
2018	498	1 242	10 614	15	5 076
Ural District					
2015	1 608	1 760	12 041	51	46 203
2016	2 056	1 402	12 023	3	12 486
2017	674	1 038	18 381	10	14 709
2018	999	1 180	17 634	41	22 632
Siberian District					
2015	3 301	7 069	13 659	3	25 729
2016	1 226	6 031	9 627	4	10 742
2017	476	3 758	14 484	18	11 411
2018	770	3 355	11 364	5	6 835
Far Eastern District					
2015	745	27 232	31 402	0	15 430
2016	316	14 742	22 239	-	4 253
2017	314	23 244	12 943	2	8 452
2018	579	23 683	12 600	-	2 070

Regional differences are noted, for example, a significant increase in the prevalence of amphetamines and a sharp decrease in synthetic cannabinoids in the Central Administrative District of RF, as well as high levels of spice prevalence, while opiates are insignificant, in the Far Eastern District. It should be noted that in both administrative districts, cocaine prevalence levels in recent years are close to zero.

Pearson's correlation coefficients for the structure of the prevalence of surfactants by administrative districts reveal the presence of significant differences in the indicators of the Far Eastern, North Caucasian and North-Western districts compared with the figures for RF as a whole, which, apparently, is determined by both regional characteristics of preferred consumption and the characteristics of the work of special services (Table 5).

Table 5: Pearson correlation coefficients for the prevalence of PAS in RF in 2015-2018.

Years	Central District	Northwest District	North Caucasus District	Southern District	Volga region	Ural District	Siberian District	Far Eastern District
2015	0,91	0,49	0,49	0,83	0,89	0,97	0,99	0,39
2016	0,89	0,84	0,48	0,61	0,96	0,97	0,95	0,22
2017	0,94	0,92	0,67	0,98	0,73	0,96	0,97	0,34
2018	0,90	0,43	0,82	0,98	0,99	0,77	0,99	0,15

Changing the structure of the withdrawn PAS when switching from measurement of absolute weight on prevalence rates in conventional doses per 100 000 population, for RF and the Central District are shown in (Figures 1-2).

Figure 1: The structure of seized PAS in RF in 2015-2018 (on the left - in the weight indicator, on the right - prevalence levels in c.d.)

Figure 2: The structure of seized PAS in the Central District in 2015-2018 (on the left - in the weight indicator, on the right - prevalence levels in c.d.)

It becomes clear that amphetamines (including synthetic cathinones) do not predominate in the structure of seizures in RF, and their specific gravity tends to increase. Synthetic cannabinoids (“spice”) also have a significantly larger specific gravity in the seizure structure than the weight analysis shows. However, their prevalence tends to decrease. The rates for opiates and cocaine are virtually unchanged. In the Central District, the overwhelming prevalence of amphetamines is noted, and the prevalence of cannabinoids is significantly lower than in RF. Spice consumption has declined rapidly in recent years.

Discussion of the Results

The results of the study show that the data on the weight indicator of PAS withdrawn from illegal trafficking does not reflect the degree of danger of individual drugs. Our proposed methodology for assessing the prevalence of surfactants from information on their seizure provides a more reliable picture of the spectrum and extent of consumption of controlled substances. This approach can be used in the overall integrated assessment when monitoring the drug situation at the federal and regional levels.

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